

Interview Australian War Memorial, Canberra - George Bailey, Senior Objects Conservator
22.12.2021

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Updated: 2021-07-28

WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys_ Guidelines for interviews.

- Presentation of the institution :

The Australian War Memorial (AWM) is primarily an institution for commemoration of Australians who have fought in war. The secondary function is as a museum.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project ? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection ? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach ? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

The AWM does not search for aircraft wrecks. In the past, aircraft wrecks have been recovered by other individuals or organisations and either sold or donated to the AWM.

- Concept of “conservation” : Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle ? How do you define long term ? What does the idea of “conservation” mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Yes, we do think about long term conservation of artefacts. For myself, long term means at least 100 years. Conservation to the AWM means retaining as much original material as possible, as long as it is safe for staff and visitors. This definition has not changed in the 30 years that I have worked at the AWM.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

Conservators and technical staff with aviation background both work on historic aircraft at the AWM. Volunteers also assist on some projects. Conservators have formal university training, and usually also have a trade background. Technical staff usually have recognised trade qualifications. We try to have both conservators and technical staff work together on projects.

In the past, technical staff have been external to the AWM, but in the past 20 years we have moved away from using external contractors where possible.

Museum Management tend to determine what projects occur, depending on upcoming exhibition needs and/or state of deterioration and therefore urgency of preservation needs of particular artefacts.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

We have WWII aircraft that are nearly complete and wrecks. All are subjected to periodic preventive conservation. Aircraft of display receive more frequent preventive conservation than those in storage. No aircraft are displayed or stored outdoors.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

We strive to maintain standard museum conditions (22°C, 50% Relative Humidity) in both display and storage areas.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant) ? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A) ?

One of the difficulties I have faced is convincing aircraft technicians working on museum aircraft that corroded aluminium components in museum aircraft do not necessarily need to be replaced or extensively mechanically and chemically treated, as they would if they were flying aircraft.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections ?

I would like to know more about the long term affects of suspending aircraft. Does stress corrosion pose a problem in these situations?

I am also interested in learning more about conserving magnesium alloys used in aircraft.

Yes, I do keep in contact with other stakeholders in this field, both conservation and aviation, and yes my practice has evolved due to these connections.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

We are currently developing an exhibition regarding the Australian participation in RAF Bomber Command operations during WW II. We have also had extensive displays on air power in the Asia Pacific region during the 1940's.